

Milestone: M2.4: Community engagement scoreboard updated

Lead Participant: CERTH

Author: Federica Quaglia, Fotis Psomopoulos

Due: 31 January 2026 (M24)

Date Of Completion: 29/01/2026

Means of Verification

[WP2 M2.4: Community Engagement Scoreboard updated](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

NO

Project participants & others

STEERS WP2 Leads: Federica Quaglia, Fotis Psomopoulos

WP2 members

ELIXIR Communities representatives

Next action steps

5-funded Communities talks at STEERS WP2 monthly meetings (starting September 2026) with updates and reporting of their Community best practices around Research Software and Workflows; the content will feed into ELIXIR-STEERS *D2.2: Research software and workflows best-practice toolkit*

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